

Mahalin ang Sariling Wika: Exploring the Filipino Language Usage, Relevance, and Importance in the Academic Context as Perceived by Students

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Abstract. This study aimed to explore how the Filipino language is perceived by senior high school students of Mindanao State University–Sulu, particularly in terms of its usage, relevance, and importance in the academic context. A case study research design was employed to allow an in-depth exploration of students' perceptions and lived academic experiences within their specific learning environment. The participants included 5 Grade-12 students and 5 Grade-11 students from both the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) and General Academic (GAS) strands, selected through purposive sampling to ensure that individuals with relevant academic exposure and communication experiences were included in the study. Data were gathered through semi-structured, face-to-face interviews with audio recordings, allowing participants to freely express their thoughts while still being guided by key questions. The data collected were then transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns, similarities, and meaningful themes among the students' responses. Findings revealed that Filipino functions as a medium of learning and academic engagement, facilitating comprehension, expression, and participation in classroom activities. Many students reported that the use of Filipino helps them better understand complex lessons, especially when concepts are difficult to grasp in English. It further argued that students' understanding of lessons is closely tied to their language proficiency, which significantly influences their overall academic development, with those more familiar with Filipino demonstrating greater ease in expressing ideas, participating in discussions, and sometimes engaging in code-switching between Filipino and English as a strategy to bridge gaps in understanding. In addition, Filipino serves as a symbol of collective identity and national belonging, reinforcing cultural awareness and social cohesion among students. It also plays an important role in fostering inclusivity in classroom interactions, especially in multilingual settings where students come from diverse linguistic backgrounds. Overall, the study highlights that Filipino is both a vital educational tool and a powerful marker of cultural and national identity.

Keywords: Code-Switching; Cultural Identity; Filipino Language; National Identity

Introduction

Language plays a vital role in shaping communication, culture and identity. Bulado et al. (2024) mentioned in their study that Filipino language was perceived not solely as a functional medium of communication but as an integral repository of the Philippines historical narratives, collective memory, and cultural ethos. This highlighted the significance of the Filipino language as more than a tool for communication, but as a vital component of cultural identity and national solidarity.

However, with the continuous honing of students' skills and proficiency in the universal language, the Filipino language faces many challenges in its application, specifically in academic context. The study of Chavez et al. (2025) highlighted how the pervasive influence of English in global communication, as well as the prestige associated with English proficiency in academic and professional settings, has led to the erosion of the Filipino language among younger generations. In addition, the study of Filipino Language in the Era of Digitalization emphasizes that one of the challenges and opportunities facing Filipino language in the academic context during the digital age are lack of materials written in Filipino on digital platforms, it poses a barrier to student learning, resulting in lower levels of comprehension and proficiency in their native language (Aranas, 2025). Esclares and Limpot (2025) also stated that one of the main reasons why many students struggle with Filipino is the lack of sufficient exposure to the language. This lack of knowledge and skills in the language is due to limited usage, even in Filipino subjects. Moreover, a lack of interest in learning the Filipino language has become a problem because students don't see its importance, instead prioritizing

English over their native language. They have eternalized the idea that English is the most widely used medium in all fields and a marker of competence. Conversely, other study suggested that some students prefer using Filipino language in academic settings. For instance, based on the findings of Bernal et al. (2024), Senior High School students at UM Digos exhibit a high level of proficiency when using the Filipino language in academic communication.

This study addresses a gap that explores the perception of the students in the usage, relevance, and importance of the Filipino language in the academic context that will be conducted in the unique environment of Mindanao State University Sulu, specifically in Senior High School Department.

Filipino is a native language that people use to communicate in the Philippines. Beyond its impact on shaping cultural identity, it also significantly influences education, particularly in students' academic context, the use of Filipino language can enhance understanding, promote cultural identity, and foster a sense of community, ultimately leading to improved academic performance and a more inclusive learning environment.

This study aims to explore if the native language still has place in the students' academic life, specifically their perception of the usage, relevance, and importance of the Filipino language despite the influence of the national language.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study is to determine the perceptions of senior high school students in the usage, relevance, and importance of Filipino language in their academic context. Specifically, this aims to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the specific contexts and frequency of Filipino language usage by students within their academic courses and disciplines?
2. How do students perceive the relevance of the Filipino language in their daily academic engagement?
3. How do students consider the Filipino language as an important medium in their academic activities?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study focused on the perceptions of Senior High School students regarding the usage, relevance, and importance of the Filipino language in the academic context at Mindanao State University-Sulu during the Academic Year 2025–2026. It specifically explored how students use Filipino in learning, communication, and classroom activities. The participants of the study were Grade 11 and Grade 12 students from the STEM and GAS strands. Ten (10) students were selected through purposive sampling. The study used a qualitative case study design and collected data through semi-structured interviews with open-ended questions. This study was limited only to selected Senior High School students of Mindanao State University-Sulu. It focused only on students' perceptions and experiences and did not measure actual language proficiency or academic performance. The findings may not represent all students in other schools or areas.

Literature Review

Language plays an important role in communication, learning, and cultural identity. In the Philippines, the Filipino language is not only used as a medium of communication but also serves as a symbol of national identity and unity. According to Bulado et al. (2024), Filipino language reflects the country's cultural heritage, collective experiences, and social values. Anderson (2006) further explained that language strengthens people's sense of belonging and national identity. In the academic context, Filipino helps students express their ideas more confidently and clearly, especially when discussing concepts connected to their own experiences and culture. Studies also showed that students understand lessons better when teachers use a familiar language because it promotes comprehension and active participation in classroom discussions (Cummins, 1979; Garcia et al., 2025).

Several studies emphasized the relevance of Filipino language in education and academic communication. Ranque et al. (2024) found that students demonstrate proficiency in using Filipino in academic communication, particularly in subjects that involve critical thinking and discussions such as Social Science, Literature, and Philosophy. Filipino also supports effective oral and written communication because students are more comfortable expressing themselves using a familiar language (Mangila, 2018). In multilingual classrooms, students commonly practice code-switching or the combination of Filipino and English to improve understanding and interaction (Bautista, 2004). Vygotsky (1978) explained that language plays a central role in cognitive development because learners acquire knowledge through communication and social interaction. Through Filipino, students can participate more actively in discussions, ask questions confidently, and better understand difficult lessons.

Despite its importance, the Filipino language faces several challenges in academic settings due to the growing dominance of English. Chavez et al. (2025) stated that many students prefer English because it is

associated with academic success and global opportunities. Aranas and Orbia (2025) also noted that there is a lack of educational materials written in Filipino, particularly in digital platforms, which limits students' exposure to the language. Esclares and Limpot (2025) added that Filipino is often limited to Filipino subjects, while English is more commonly used in other disciplines such as Mathematics and Science. However, studies revealed that Filipino remains important in promoting cultural identity, national pride, and effective communication among students. These studies support the present research in exploring students' perceptions regarding the usage, relevance, and importance of Filipino language in their academic context.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a Case Study Research Design. A case study is a Qualitative approach in which the investigator explores a real-life, contemporary bounded system (a cases) or multiple bounded systems (cases) over time through detailed, in-depth data collection involving multiple sources of information (Creswell, 2014). This Research Design used to explore the "Perception of the students in the Filipino language usage, relevance, and importance in the academic context.

Sampling Design

This study used purposive sampling in selecting the participants. The respondents were Grade 11 and Grade 12 students from the STEM and GAS strands of Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School during the Academic Year 2025–2026. A total of ten (10) students were selected from the total population of 558 students. The participants were chosen based on their interest and participation in the Filipino language subject. Purposive sampling was used because the selected students could provide relevant information and experiences about the usage, relevance, and importance of the Filipino language in their academic context.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School, located within the Mindanao State University campus at Capitol Site, Patikul, Sulu. Established in 1974, the university has continually provided opportunities for learning and development in the province. The Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School Department was established in 2016. The department is near the campus gymnasium. It offers two academic strands, Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) and General Academic Strand (GAS) from which the participants of this study will be selected.

Research Participants

The chosen respondents of this study were Grade 11 and 12 students from the Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) and General Academic Strand (GAS) at the Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School for the Academic Year 2025-2026. The study involved 10 respondents out of a total of 558 students selected through Purposive Sampling. The researchers chose this approach because participants are selected based on those who show interest or give an outstanding performance in Filipino Language.

Research Instrument

Data needed for this study was gathered through semi-structured interviews, direct face-to-face interview with audio recording between the researchers and the participant with the use of Open-Ended Questions. Conducted conversationally with one respondent at a time, the semi-structured interview (SSI) employs an open-ended questions, often accompanied by follow-up why or how questions (Adams, 2015).

Data Gathering Procedures

The study sought for ethical approval from the respondents before any data collection begin. Data collection is planned over a two weeks period, with interview during scheduled class sessions. Data is stored securely, accessible only to the research group for academic purposes.

Results and Discussions

Illuminating the students' school experiences alongside the Filipino language, the findings revealed five themes within the academic context that answer the question: How is the Filipino language used, perceived, and experienced by students within academic contexts in terms of learning and comprehension, relevance across various subjects, academic communication, challenges encountered, and the use of code-switching?

The findings was also able to unveil two themes that extend beyond academic settings, addressing the question: How do students perceive the importance of Filipino language as a national language, and how do they promote its continued and preservation?

Filipino Usage in Academic Learning and Comprehension

The Filipino Language is not only a symbol of national identity but also a vital instrument that shapes students' academic learning and comprehension. Its continued use in educational contexts highlights its relevance and significant influence on students in their daily learning at school. It makes it easier for them to understand complex lessons especially those taught in other mediums like English, develop clear concepts and further enrich their foundational knowledge of their native language.

Students' responses reveal that Filipino serves as an effective medium of instruction that enhance comprehension. By using a familiar language, learners are able to connect new knowledge with prior understanding, making learning more accessible and meaningful. One respondent highlighted the important role of the Filipino language as a support system in students' learning, especially for those who are not highly proficient in English.

"The Filipino language plays an important role in helping students, especially those with limited English vocabulary, better understand lessons when explanations and examples are elaborated in Filipino. It allows us to more easily grasp what the teacher is teaching while also helping us express and develop our own ideas and opinions more effectively."(R2)

The statement implies that language can be a barrier to understanding. When lessons are delivered purely in English, students with limited vocabulary may struggle to follow discussions. Because of this, using Filipino helps bridge the gap by making explanations clearer and more relatable.

Another respondent emphasizes how Filipino is used as a tool for translation, particularly when students encounter unfamiliar or difficult terms, allowing students to better understand unfamiliar or complex terms by relating them to their native language.

"It can contribute in definition of terms, like example, if there's a word that is unfamiliar, then when the teacher used Filipino to translate it or define it, understanding becomes much easier and simpler." (R8)

This response indicates that vocabulary is a common source of confusion in the classroom. When students come across words they do not recognize, it can interrupt their understanding of the entire lesson. However, when the teacher translates or explains these terms in Filipino, the meaning becomes clearer and easier to grasp.

Beyond its functional role in learning, Filipino also contributes to comprehensive development by enabling students to confidently ask questions and seek clarification. One student highlighted the role of Filipino in promoting clear communication and active participation among fellow students.

"During activities, if you can't understand a classmate's report, you can ask questions using Filipino because it lets you express what you want to say or clarify." (R6)

This statement suggests that Filipino helps reduce communication barriers during class interactions, such as reports or group activities. When students use a language they are confident in, they are more likely to ask questions because they can express their thoughts more easily leading to a more profound lesson comprehension.

Additionally, the usage of Filipino in written context helps sustain students' interest in reading by making content more relatable and comprehensible. Capturing the attention of readers is a major challenge for a writer, and one of the factors to consider is the language to be used. Through Filipino, students can more easily understand the context of what they are reading without the need for deep explanations as reported by one of the respondents.

"Most readers, they kind of lost interest if they cannot comprehend the context written, especially if the words are complex, so it's better to use Filipino for them not to lose interest." (R8)

This statement conveys that using Filipino can make reading more accessible. When ideas are presented in a familiar language, students can better understand the context, making the reading experience smoother and more enjoyable.

All in all, these findings demonstrate that Filipino language plays a multifaceted role in education. It facilitates learning, supports effective comprehension, and fosters active participation and engagement among students.

Relevance of Filipino Across Different Subjects

Language plays a crucial role in how knowledge is delivered and understood across various subjects. While English is often used as the primary medium of instruction and Filipino is most prominently utilized in Filipino as a subject, it also extends to other disciplines such as Social Science, Literature, and Philosophy as provided by students.

"I usually use Filipino in our subjects like Social Science, known for having a wide variety of lectures, so it really needs a good explanation." (R8)

This statement indicates that in subjects like Social Science, where lessons often involve complex ideas, concepts, and extensive discussions, students find it easier to rely on Filipino for clearer understanding. The mention of "a wide variety of lectures" suggests that the subject covers many topics, making comprehension more challenging if only English is used.

"It is not just a language taught in Filipino class; it also includes lessons about Philippine literature and history, helping us understand the country's events and past." (R10)

This answer from a student implies that Filipino also covers important cultural and historical content, such as Philippine literature and history. This shows that learning in Filipino involves more than grammar and vocabulary, it also includes understanding the nation's identity and heritage.

"For me Filipino is relevant to use in Philosophical matters. Since in Philosophy, it teaches virtues and human behaviors so we are able to communicate effectively if we use Filipino Language." (R9)

This idea from a learner further conveyed the perceived usefulness of Filipino in understanding and discussing abstract and reflective subjects like Philosophy. The student sees Filipino as an effective medium for discussing philosophical ideas. Since Philosophy often deals with deep and complex concepts, using a familiar language makes these ideas easier to express and understand.

In conclusion, these responses show that the Filipino language is not limited to being just a subject in the curriculum, but also serves as a meaningful medium of instruction across various disciplines. Therefore, Filipino continues to play an important role in making education more accessible, relevant, and meaningful for learners.

Filipino Usage in Academic Communication

Filipino language serves as an essential medium for both oral and written communication in academic settings. In oral communication, students use Filipino to express their thoughts, emotions, and insights during discussions, recitations, and presentations. Many respondents noted that they feel comfortable when using Filipino, enabling them to communicate more naturally and confidently.

"Filipino language allows us to express our thoughts more easily, being able to speak it clearly is important during oral recitations because it helps us explain our ideas better." (R10)

This statement shows that students find it easier to organize and communicate their thoughts when using Filipino. Because it is a familiar language, they can focus more on the content of their ideas rather than struggling with vocabulary or grammar. Another respondent tells that communication becomes more effective not only for the speaker but also for the listener.

"Usually when I use Filipino, I find myself being able to express myself well and the ones I am talking to are able to follow what I am trying to say." (R8)

This report from a student suggests that the speaker feels more confident when using Filipino, as it allows them to express their thoughts more smoothly and naturally. Because they are comfortable with the language, they can organize their ideas better while speaking.

When it comes to written communication, Filipino serves as a helpful tool for expressing ideas more clearly and effectively in written form. This response emphasizes the importance of Filipino in supporting students' academic writing skills.

"The Filipino language is crucial as it helps us with academic writing. We use it to further express our thoughts, opinions, and ideas on a particular topic because we are more familiar with it." (R2) (R6) (R10)

This statement demonstrates that language familiarity directly influences writing quality. When students use Filipino, they are less restricted by vocabulary limitations, allowing them to focus more on content, ideas, and meaning rather than struggling with language structure.

Overall, the findings reveal that Filipino language takes a vital role in both oral and written communication in academic settings. Its use allows students to express their thoughts more clearly, confidently, and effectively, as it reduces the challenges associated with limited vocabulary and language barriers.

Academic Challenges of Filipino Language

Despite being the native language of the Filipino people, the Filipino language still faces several challenges in its application among the youth in academics. One of the primary issues identified by the findings is the difficulty experienced by some students in understanding and speaking the Filipino language. One respondent highlighted that they struggle to comprehend lessons when Filipino is used as the medium of instruction in other subjects, particularly in Mathematics.

"I use Filipino the least in Mathematics because I cannot understand some concepts when they are explained in Filipino." (R1)

This suggests that numerical and conceptual discussions become more difficult to grasp when delivered in Filipino. The challenge is not only limited to academic contexts but also extends to everyday communication. The respondent further shared that understanding conversations in Filipino can be difficult when interacting with others who primarily use the language.

"If I encounter someone who speaks Filipino, it can be difficult for me to understand." (R1)

This indicates that despite living in the Philippines, some students are still not fully familiar or comfortable with their native language. For instance, another respondent expressed difficulty in speaking due to struggles with pronouncing certain words.

"I can personally say that I cannot really speak well in either English or Filipino because there are certain words that I struggle to pronounce." (R2)

This implies that the speaker experiences difficulty in speaking both languages fluently. This also suggests that language proficiency is not only about understanding or vocabulary, but also about the ability to articulate words clearly and confidently. Even if a learner understands the language, difficulty in pronunciation can still affect overall academic communication performance.

The widespread of English has also gradually overshadowed the Filipino language, resulting in its reduced usage. Due to this, students tend to distance themselves from their native language. The lack of consistent use of Filipino contributes to the decline in students' language proficiency that results in the difficulties of understanding and speaking Filipino effectively.

"Nowadays, Filipino is not really used that much anymore, children mostly use the universal language and neglect the use of the Filipino language. If we consider that English is more emphasized, I can't deny that it's harder for me to understand things in Filipino compared to English." (R3)

This conveys the idea that English has become more dominant in everyday communication and education, leading to a reduced use of Filipino among children. As a result, Filipino is becoming less practiced in some contexts.

The findings also reflect that limitation of Filipino language in academic settings is also one of the major challenges faced by the native language. Students lack sufficient exposure to Filipino, contributing to their limited proficiency as Filipino is often confined to Filipino-related subjects and is rarely utilized in other areas of instruction.

"I think the Filipino language is only relevant in Filipino subjects because the usage of it is limited when it comes to other subjects." (R2)

This suggests that Filipino is perceived as a subject-specific language rather than a general medium of instruction across disciplines. It reflects the idea that other subjects are more commonly taught in English, which can make Filipino feel less useful.

The findings further revealed that teachers' encouragement to use English imposes certain restrictions on students' use of Filipino in English-related subjects. This limits students' ability to freely apply Filipino in expressing their thoughts and understanding of the lessons. One student shared how teacher instruction and subject expectations influence language use in the classroom.

"The least that we use Filipino is in Creative Writing because our teacher encouraged us to speak using the English language." (R2)

This statement indicates that in subjects where English is prioritized as the medium of instruction and expression, the teacher encourages its use, so students naturally reduce their use of Filipino in that subject.

To sum up, the findings pointed out that despite being the native language, Filipino faces significant challenges in its use among students in academic contexts. Difficulties in comprehension, pronunciation, and expression show that some learners are not fully proficient or comfortable using Filipino. These challenges are further intensified by the growing dominance of English, which has become the more commonly used language in both education and daily interactions.

Use of Code-Switching

Despite the challenges the findings revealed, that Filipino still plays an important role as a supportive and complementary language in a multilingual environment. Students frequently engage in code-switching, combining Filipino, English, and even regional languages such as Sinug to facilitate understanding and communication. Code-switching serves as a practical strategy for overcoming linguistic limitations as shared by two students.

"I sometimes use Filipino when I cannot express something in English, but I still end up using the vernacular language, I also used English but still mixed with Filipino." (R5) (R6)

This indicates that the student relies on Filipino as a support when they struggle to express themselves in English. This shows that Filipino serves as a fallback language that helps them continue communicating when they cannot find the right English words. One of the respondents also tells that they used Taglish (a mix of Filipino and English) for a relaxed approach to language use.

"I use Filipino in explaining, sometimes in writing we are allowed to do Taglish." (R8)

This suggests that there is some level of acceptance of Taglish in writing tasks. Strict language boundaries are sometimes relaxed to allow students to express their thoughts more naturally and effectively.

In general, the findings established the concept of Filipino as an essential supportive language in a multilingual academic setting. Rather than functioning as a stand-alone medium, it is frequently used in combination with English and regional languages through code-switching.

Importance of Filipino as the National Language

Filipino, like any other language, serves as a key instrument in fostering unity and solidarity among people, particularly in the Philippines. Beyond being a medium of communication, it plays a vital role in social interaction and interpersonal relationships by serving as a bridge that connects individuals from different regions and linguistic backgrounds. More importantly, it is perceived as a symbol of cultural identity and national belonging. The ability to speak and understand Filipino is closely associated with being recognized as part of the Filipino community. In this sense, language becomes a marker of identity, where lack of proficiency may lead to feelings of embarrassment or perceived detachment from one's cultural roots, as expressed by one respondent.

"It's embarrassing because if you are Filipino but you don't know how to use the Filipino language, you cannot truly be called Filipino if you don't even know how to communicate with your fellow Filipinos using your own native language." (R1)

This suggests that there is a sense of social expectation or pressure to know and use Filipino. Not being able to speak it may lead to feelings of embarrassment or inadequacy, as it can be seen as disconnect from one's cultural roots.

As stated by one respondent, Filipino is not only used in academic settings but it is also actively utilized in everyday encounters to ensure mutual understanding, especially when interacting with people from different cities or provinces. In a nation characterized by regional, cultural, and linguistic diversity, the national language serves as a common ground that bridges communication gaps among Filipinos.

"Using Filipino isn't just something I do in school, I also use it with people I encounter everyday to make sure we understand each other. It's helpful in many situations beyond academics, like when I'm interacting with other Filipinos from different cities or provinces. Filipino is the bridge that allows us to communicate no matter where we are here in the Philippines." (R5)

This statement conveys the idea of the national language serving as a common ground among Filipinos, especially when interacting with individuals from different cities or provinces who may have different local dialects.

On the whole, Filipino language functions not only as a medium of communication but also as a powerful symbol of national identity and social unity. It serves as a linguistic bridge that enables effective interaction among Filipinos from diverse regional backgrounds. At the same time, it carries strong social expectations, where proficiency in it is often associated with cultural belonging, and limited ability may lead to perceived detachment.

Encouragement of Filipino Language Usage and Preservation

The importance of preserving the Filipino language also emerged as a significant concern among the students. They emphasized that maintaining the language is essential in sustaining cultural identity, as it defines who they are as individuals. The following statements encourages the youth, in particular, to take pride in and value the language, recognizing it as a representation of their heritage and collective identity.

"As Filipinos we should take pride in having our own national language, and it is because, it is our national language, for that, we have to love it." (R5) (R7)

This response from a student indicates that Filipinos should learn how to value their national language because it represent the nation as a whole. Being the national language gives Filipino a sense of importance that goes beyond everyday communication, leading to the suggestion of one of the respondents to preserve the native language.

"We should preserve our own language, because it defines who we are, it is our identity as Filipino citizens." (R3)

The respondent views the Filipino language as a defining element of what it means to be a Filipino and suggests that preserving the language is essential in maintaining a strong sense of national identity.

"As a student, I encourage and support the usage of Filipino language...I encourage its use so people can express themselves effectively." (R6)

This statement shows that students not only value Filipino but also promote its use among others. This indicates a sense of responsibility in encouraging the continued use of the language.

The strong support of teachers in promoting and reinforcing the use of the Filipino language within the school—especially in Filipino subjects—is one of the seen factors that encourages the youth to further

appreciate, uphold, and continuously improve their use of the national language in both academic and everyday contexts as shared by two students.

"I often use the Filipino language in Filipino subjects because our teacher encourages us to use Filipino, emphasizing that it is essential for us to become proficient in it." (R2) (R5)

This suggests that the use of Filipino in class is not just for compliance but is being actively promoted as a tool for learning. It indicates that the teacher values Filipino as an important medium encouraging the students on its continued use for proficiency, confidence, and deeper understanding.

Overall, students place importance on preserving the Filipino language as a core element of cultural identity and national pride. Filipino is seen as a symbol that represents what it means to be Filipino.

On the whole, these findings unfold the reality that the Filipino language still holds a place in students' perspectives. They perceived it as a vital language in education as it enhances comprehension, supports communication, and strengthens cultural identity. However, its usage is challenged by the dominance of English and limited exposure in some academic areas. Despite these challenges, students continue to value Filipino as a symbol of national identity that should be promoted and preserved.

Ethical Considerations

Respondents were fully informed of the study's purpose, and written consent is obtained, assuring that participation is voluntary and based on a clear understanding of the research. All responses were kept anonymous and handled with honesty and integrity, ensuring that all respondents' answers are truthful and accurate. Respondents were also assured that they have the right to withdraw at any time without any negative consequences.

Conclusion

The Filipino language is perceived as an effective medium that influences students' comprehension, expression, and overall academic development. Students' familiarity with the Filipino language helps them understand lessons more easily and communicate their ideas more effectively and confidently. Filipino also serves as a bridge in understanding complex topics, especially when students encounter challenges with the English language. However, in certain contexts, the Filipino language can be difficult to use as a medium of instruction, particularly in subjects such as Mathematics. This reflects how language exposure and usage shape academic proficiency. Despite this, Filipino remains a valuable linguistic tool, especially through practices like code-switching, which enable students to express ideas more clearly and enhance comprehension. Rather than viewing Filipino and English as competing languages, the findings suggest that they function more effectively as complementary mediums of instruction. In addition, the Filipino language plays an important role in bridging dialects across the country, serving as a unifying medium among Filipinos. Beyond communication, it stands as a powerful marker of national and cultural identity, reinforcing a sense of belonging. Its use in showing respect, preserving traditions, and expressing cultural nuances further strengthens its significance beyond academics. Overall, Filipino remains an essential unifying force that connects individuals across differences, fostering national unity while preserving cultural identity. Filipino language extends beyond just an academic language, enabling both preservation of cultural identity and bridging dialects across regions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers highly recommend that the administration of Mindanao State University-Sulu strengthen and institutionalize programs, policies, and academic initiatives that promote the continuous use, development, and preservation of the Filipino language within the school community. The university may establish a more comprehensive language policy that supports the use of Filipino not only in Filipino subjects but also in academic activities, official communications, research presentations, campus programs, and scholarly publications. The administration is further encouraged to provide institutional support through seminars, conferences, research incentives, and the development of localized instructional materials written in Filipino to encourage both students and faculty members to actively participate in the intellectualization of the national language. Faculty members are likewise encouraged to integrate Filipino effectively in classroom instruction by applying bilingual or multilingual teaching strategies that can improve students' comprehension, confidence, classroom participation, and critical thinking skills. Teachers may also create learning environments where students feel comfortable expressing their ideas in Filipino, especially in discussions involving local culture, experiences, and social realities. In addition, students are encouraged to actively uphold and utilize Filipino in academic discussions, written outputs, collaborative learning activities, and everyday communication to strengthen their appreciation of the national language, cultural identity, and sense of nationalism. The continuous use of Filipino among students may also help preserve linguistic traditions and promote clearer and more meaningful communication in academic settings. Furthermore, future researchers are encouraged to conduct

more extensive studies involving larger populations, different academic programs, and various educational institutions to further examine the relevance, challenges, and evolving role of the Filipino language in academic and multilingual contexts. Future studies may also explore additional variables such as language proficiency, academic performance, digital communication, and the influence of social media and globalization on students' language preferences and practices.

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